

1 **The levels of artificial insemination and missing sire information make genomic**
2 **selection not always beneficial in meat sheep**

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9 Short title: genomic selection for meat sheep

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12 **Abstract**

13 Numerous meat sheep breeding programs in developed and developing countries are
14 characterized by incomplete sire information and a predominant use of natural
15 matings. These two parameters potentially affect the benefit of genomic selection,
16 especially for the selection of a late-in-life trait. Using stochastic simulations, the
17 genetic gains obtained using genomic and conventional strategies for a maternal trait
18 were evaluated in meat sheep population. Natural mating and artificial insemination
19 based designs, inspired by the current diversity of designs used for French meat sheep
20 breeds, were modelled and three genomic strategies were tested and compared with
21 a conventional selection strategy: parentage assignment, genomic selection based on
22 a male or a male and female reference population. Genomic selection based on a male
23 reference population did not always outperform conventional selection. Its benefit
24 depended on the design, the level of missing information on dam sires and the level of
25 artificial insemination. Genomic selection based on a male and female reference

26 population always outperformed the conventional selection strategy, even if only 25%
27 of the females in the nucleus were genotyped.

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30 **Keywords:** small ruminants, breeding program, stochastic simulations, genomic
31 selection, genetic gain

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34 **Implications**

35 This simulation study assesses selection strategies for meat sheep populations
36 characterized by incomplete pedigree information and a predominant or exclusive use
37 of natural matings. The results make it possible to evaluate the benefit of moving to
38 genomic selection and to optimize its deployment in these populations.

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41 **Introduction**

42 Genomic selection (GS) seems promising for the selection of lowly heritable and / or
43 late-in-life traits (Schaeffer 2006, Meuwissen et al., 2013) and has been widely adopted
44 in dairy cattle (Pryce *et al.*, 2012) and other species. If the accuracy of the genomic
45 estimated breeding values (GEBV) is sufficient, GS allows early selection on traits
46 measured later in life and is therefore an alternative to progeny testing. Genotyping
47 animals could also be used to assign parentage to animals born from multi-sire
48 matings. Thus GS can be particularly beneficial to select maternal traits for meat sheep
49 breeding programs. Yet, only a few countries have implemented GS for meat sheep
50 on a wide scale (Swan et al., 2010; Pickering et al., 2013). Reviewed by Rupp *et al.*

51 (2016), several factors limit the benefit of GS for these populations: the populations
52 are generally small, their effective sizes tend to be large, with a negative effect on
53 GEBV precision and the quality of phenotypes (accuracy of sire genetic values) is
54 limited due to the low AI (Artificial Insemination) rate. Another difficulty is high cost of
55 genotyping as compared to the animals' market values.

56 Previous studies have assessed selection strategies based on genomic selection for
57 meat sheep in Australia (Granleese *et al.*, 2015), New Zealand (Santos *et al.*, 2017)
58 and France (Shumbusho *et al.*, 2009; Raoul *et al.*, 2017). These studies demonstrated
59 the benefits of GS but the sensitivity of the results to various levels of AI and pedigree
60 knowledge needs to be assessed to support breeding societies in their decision to
61 implement GS. The aim of this study was to assess the benefit of using genomic
62 information (parentage assignment and GS) for the selection of a repeated maternal
63 trait according a range of AI rates and pedigree knowledge levels. Using stochastic
64 simulations, we modelled conventional strategies for meat sheep breeding programs
65 and some genomic alternatives, such as parentage assignment, male reference
66 populations and male and female reference populations.

67

68 **Material and Methods**

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70

71 *Simulation overview.*

72 To consider various organizations, three conventional designs inspired by the French
73 meat sheep breeding programs (Supplementary Material S1, Supplementary Table
74 S1) were modelled: a natural mating based breeding program (NM) and two AI based
75 breeding programs with or without progeny testing (PT) of AI sires (NM+AI+PT,

76 NM+AI). A maternal trait was the unique selection criterion in this study. We first
77 established founder populations and ran breeding programs for 10 years with a
78 conventional strategy (CS) to obtain populations close to the existing ones. We then
79 applied for the following 15 years either the same strategy (CS) or an alternative one:
80 a parentage assignment (PAR_AS) or a GS strategy based on a reference population
81 built either with only genotyped males (GS_M) or with genotyped males and females
82 (GS_MF). For AI based breeding programs, GS strategies were identical regardless of
83 the previous CS (NM+AI or NM+AI+PT).

84 We derived input parameters for CS simulations from Supplementary Table S1 and
85 analysis of the French official genetic database. The level of AI (% of dams inseminated
86 each year) was derived from the % of lambs born from inseminated ewes and the
87 fertility after AI per breed. The percentage of dams with sire information was linked to
88 the proportion of lambs with sire information. To limit computation time, only scenarii
89 that were relevant for the French industry were simulated. In total, we simulated 73
90 scenarii. For the NM design, 18 scenarii were defined: 5 CS, 4 PAR_AS, 5 GS_M and
91 4 GS_MF depending on the % of dams with sire information and the % of genotyped
92 dams (Table 1). For the current NM+AI design, 30 scenarii were defined: 6 CS, 6
93 PAR_AS, 6 GS_M and 12 GS_MF depending on the AI level, the % of dams with sire
94 information and the % of genotyped dams (Table 2 and 3). For the current NM+AI+PT
95 design, 25 scenarii were defined: 5 CS, 3 PAR_AS, 5 GS_M and 12 GS_MF depending
96 on the AI level, the % of dams with sire information and the % of genotyped dams
97 (Table 4 and 5).

98 We used a stochastic model coded in Fortran (founder population setup, gamete
99 production, phenotype simulations, selection steps) and Blupf90 software (Misztal *et*
100 *al.*,1994) to run the genetic evaluation based on BLUP or a single step GBLUP. This

101 model is fully described in Supplementary Material S2 and Raoul *et al.* (2017). Study
102 population genomes were derived from real 50k genotypes. One thousand markers
103 were randomly selected and assigned as QTLs. The QTL effects were drawn from a
104 Gamma distribution and the sign randomly allocated. Individual true breeding values
105 were computed according to genotypes at QTLs, assuming additivity. Individual
106 phenotypes were simulated by adding random effects (year by flock, permanent
107 environmental and residual effects) to true breeding values. Selection and matings
108 were organized using EBVs computed year by year.

109

110 *Population structure.*

111 To allow all designs assessed to be compared, a single population size of around
112 7,000 females (dams) mated annually was considered. The demographic parameters
113 were defined so that the population size remained constant across years: the
114 probabilities of survival depended on the age and sex for all individuals and the
115 reproduction type for males (natural mating or AI). All reproductive parameters such
116 as AI fertility, litter size distribution or within-litter size viability were constant across all
117 designs. The female replacement rate was also constant across strategies: 60% of
118 newborn females born from AI were candidates to replace culled dams. If AI was not
119 used or could not meet dam replacement needs, newborn females born from natural
120 mating sires were randomly kept until needs were met.

121

122 *Conventional selection strategy.*

123

124 *Natural mating based breeding programs (NM)*. In “NM programs”, AI is not used at
125 all. To mimic selection differential losses due to the breed standard or the selection of
126 functional traits, only half of newborn males (around 4,000) were supposed to be
127 candidates for selection. Based on their parents’ EBVs, the top 500 were selected
128 during their first year of life, with only a third still being candidates one year later after
129 losses due to mortality and selection on secondary traits. The best (selection on
130 parents’ EBVs) were randomly allocated to flocks according to their needs. In
131 agreement with observed practices, a male could not be allocated to the flock in which
132 he was born (self-replacement). Natural mating sires were used for four years at the
133 most. Random culling was applied according to current demographic parameters. No
134 exchanges of old males between flocks were simulated. For the conventional strategy,
135 five NM breeding programs were simulated according the proportion of dams whose
136 sire information was known (0, 25, 50, 75 or 100%).

137

138 *Animal insemination based breeding programs without progeny testing (NM+AI)*. In
139 NM+AI, one-year-old male candidates were first selected as in NM. At one year of age,
140 best ranked males were selected for AI prior to males for natural mating. AI sires were
141 used for two years at the most and mated to the best dams based on EBVs. AI matings
142 were performed at random with a maximum number of matings per AI sire dependent
143 on his age. Natural mating sires were used and replaced as in NM. Sire information
144 was always known for lambs born from AI but not always for lambs born from natural
145 mating. For the conventional selection strategy with missing sire information, four
146 NM+AI breeding programs were simulated according the proportion of inseminated
147 ewes (10, 20% per year) and the proportion of dams born from natural mating whose
148 sire information was known (0, 25%). For higher AI levels, only two NM+AI breeding

149 programs were simulated according the proportion of inseminated ewes (30 or 60%
150 per year).

151

152 *Animal insemination based breeding program with progeny testing (NM+AI+PT).* In
153 NM+AI+PT, one-year-old male candidates were selected as in NM and NM+AI and
154 males for AI were selected as in NM+AI. In their second year, the progeny testing of
155 young AI males was set up via their mating with randomly selected, non-elite dams in
156 the nucleus. In their fourth year, the first records of their daughters were available and
157 thus they were candidates to be selected as elite AI males. Elite AI males were
158 selected among these candidates and the elite AI males of the previous year. An elite
159 AI male could be used up to four times. Unselected AI males (four years old and older)
160 were culled. Dams were mated (AI or NM) at most once a year. Dams were ranked
161 according their EBVs: the best were randomly mated to elite sires and the following
162 dams were randomly mated to young AI males. Other dams and dams that did not
163 conceive to AI were then randomly mated to natural mating males present in their flock.
164 For the conventional selection strategy, three NM+AI+PT breeding programs were
165 simulated according to the proportion of inseminated ewes (30, 60 or 80% per year)
166 and one breeding program was simulated with missing sire information (AI = 30% and
167 proportion of dams born from natural mating with sire information = 25%).

168

169 *Parentage assignment strategy (PAR_AS).*

170 For populations with dams with missing sire information, we assessed the usefulness
171 of using parentage assignment based on molecular information. In the basic situation,
172 the sire was unknown for all lambs born from natural mating. Sire information was
173 determined for all one-year-old males after selection and we tested various proportions

174 of sire assignment (25, 50, 75 or 100%) for ewe-lambs replacing culled dams.
175 Parentage assignment was based on low-density genotypes (1,000 SNPs; genotyping
176 error = 0.5%) using a likelihood method derived from Tortereau *et al.* (2017). The
177 quality of the assignment was checked and no errors were observed with this number
178 of markers. In this strategy, the genomic information is not used to predict breeding
179 values and EBVs were computed based on a BLUP animal model.

180

181 *Genomic selection strategies.*

182 *Male reference population (GS_M).* This strategy is based on a male reference
183 population. When a breeding program switches to this genomic selection strategy, all
184 sires (AI and NM) used over the last 10 years are genotyped to initiate the reference
185 population. The following years, male candidates are genotyped in their first year of
186 age and male replacement (both for AI and natural mating) was based on their GEBVs.
187 Newly selected males entered the reference population. In this scenario, all individuals
188 had GEBVs as a single step GBLUP was used. AI males were mated to the dams with
189 the highest GEBVs for two years at most and then culled.

190

191 *Male and female reference population (GS_MF).* This strategy is identical to the
192 previous one for male genotypes but female genotypes were also considered. When a
193 breeding program switched to using the GS_MF strategy, a proportion (25, 50 or 100%)
194 of live dams were randomly genotyped. The following years, the same proportion of
195 ewe-lamb replacements were randomly genotyped.

196

197 *Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rate assessment.*

198 The annual genetic gain (resp. inbreeding rate) per replicate was computed as the
199 regression slope of the average true breeding value (resp. pedigree inbreeding
200 coefficient) of first parity dams over a time interval between years 10 and 25. Gains
201 are expressed in genetic standard deviation of the selected trait per year (σ_a/y).
202 Inbreeding rates were only computed for strategies where the sire information of dams
203 was completely known and expressed per year. Reported values for gains and
204 inbreeding are averages of 30 replicates.

205

206

207 **Results**

208 *Natural mating based breeding programs.*

209 The annual genetic gains for NM breeding programs are reported in Table 1 according
210 to the strategy used and the proportion of dams with sire information. For the
211 Conventional Strategy (CS), for which no genomic information was used, the higher
212 the proportion of sire information known, and the higher the annual genetic gain. The
213 increase in gain as a function of the proportion of sire information was not linear and
214 was greater as the pedigree completeness tended to higher values. Moving from the
215 case where none of the dams born from natural mating had a known sire to the case
216 where all those dams had their sire known resulted in +42% more gain. Using
217 parentage assignment (PAR_AS) provided a higher genetic gain compared with CS
218 for the same proportion of dams with sire information (except for complete pedigrees
219 that gave the same gain) because in the PAR_AS strategy the sires of all one-year-old
220 males (i.e. candidates) were assigned. With PAR_AS, the increase in gain as a
221 function of the proportion of sire information was linear.

222 The genomic selection strategy based on a male reference population (GS_M) gave a
223 higher gain than CS for the same proportion of sire information. The annual genetic
224 gain of a genomic selection strategy based on a male and female reference population
225 (GS_MF) was practically independent of the proportion of genotyped dams (0.153 -
226 0.161 σ_a/y), and higher than the gain obtained with GS_M strategies (21% to 48%
227 depending on the proportion of dams born from natural mating with sire information).

228

229 *Artificial insemination based breeding programs without progeny testing.*

230 The annual genetic gains for NM+AI programs are reported in Table 2 according to the
231 genomic strategy used for dams with missing sire information. Two “low” levels of AI
232 (% of ewes inseminated per year) were considered: 10 and 20%. Using parentage
233 assignment had a greater effect when the AI level was low. Compared with CS in which
234 females born from natural mating had no sire information, PAR_AS provided an
235 additional gain respectively of +21% and + 10% for AI levels of 10% and 20%.

236 GS_M gave a lower gain than CS strategies when females born from natural mating
237 had no sire information regardless the of AI level (-6%, AI = 10%; -7%, AI = 20%).

238 When at least 25% of females born from natural mating had sire information, GS_M
239 gave a higher gain than CS whatever the AI level (+11%, AI = 10%; +15%, AI = 20%).

240 Adding female genotypes in the reference population was always beneficial: GS_MF
241 gave similar gains regardless of the proportion of genotyped females (0.180 - 0.183
242 σ_a/y , AI = 10% ; 0.213 - 0.217 σ_a/y , AI = 20%).

243 The gains obtained for higher AI levels (30% and 60%) are reported in Table 3. In
244 these designs, most of ewe-lamb replacements were born from AI and dam sire
245 information was known. Thus, PAR_AS scenarii were useless and were not
246 considered. Regardless of the AI level, the strategies were ranked as in the pure

247 Natural Mating programs (CS < GS_M < GS_MF). The benefit of AI depended on the
248 strategy: moving from NM to NM+AI (60%) gave respectively +36% and +48% for CS
249 and GS_MF strategies.

250

251 *Artificial insemination based breeding programs with progeny testing.*

252 The annual genetic gains of NM+AI+PT breeding programs are reported in Table 4
253 according to the strategy used and the proportion of dams with sire information. Only
254 one level of AI (30%) was considered because a certain level of AI is needed to ensure
255 correct progeny testing and higher AI levels would result in complete information of
256 dam sires (all replacement females born from AI). Using PAR_AS to recover missing
257 sires had very little effect regardless of the completeness of dam sire information (25,
258 50 or 100%): from -2% to +3% compared with CS.

259 GS_M gave a lower gain (-3%) than CS when part of the dams' sire information was
260 missing but a slightly higher gain of +9% when all dam sires were known (0.191 vs
261 0.175 σ_a/y). GS_MF provided a much higher gain (+32 to +40%) than CS, but this
262 gain increased only slightly (0.224 to 0.238 σ_a/y) when the percentage of genotyped
263 females shifted from 25% to 100%.

264 The gains obtained when sire information was complete are reported in Table 5 for
265 three levels of AI (30, 60 and 80%). Compared with CS, GS_M gave a higher gain at
266 AI = 30% (+9%), a similar gain at AI = 60% and a lower gain at AI = 80% (-4%).
267 Regardless of the AI level, the gains obtained with GS_MF increased slightly as the
268 percentage of genotyped females shifted from 25% to 100%. GS_MF always gave
269 higher gains than CS but the increase in gain depended on the AI level: with 25% of
270 genotyped females, GS_MF gave +30% (AI = 30%), +26% (AI = 60%) and +15%
271 (AI = 80%) gain respectively, compared with CS.

272

273

274 **Discussion**

275 In this study, we assessed the benefits of parentage assignment and genomic
276 selection strategies for a set of meat sheep breeding programs meant to reflect a
277 diversity regarding the use of AI and the pedigree completeness. Using a stochastic
278 model, we derived the annual genetic gain of a population under selection with various
279 designs (NM, NM+AI, NM+AI+PT), proportions of known sire information, proportions
280 of inseminated ewes (AI designs only) and proportions of genotyped females for
281 genomic selection strategies.

282

283 *Benefits of parentage assignment.*

284 Parentage assignment was largely beneficial for NM as the increase in genetic gain,
285 as compared to a situation where none of the females had a known sire, reached up
286 to +40%. The benefits were less important for NM+AI (+21%, %AI = 10%; +10%,
287 %AI = 20%) and low for NM+AI+PT (+3%) designs. These results confirm the relative
288 advantage of PAR_AS strategies reported in Raoul *et al.* (2016), depending on the
289 breeding program design. The differences in gain between complete and missing sire
290 information designs for NM and NM+AI are in line with those obtained by Raoul and
291 Elsen (2019) who used a stochastic model but did not model the genomes.

292

293 *Benefit of a genomic selection strategy based on a male reference population.*

294 Switching from CS to GS_M was not always beneficial. The benefits depended on both
295 the proportion of dams with sire information and the design.

296 For NM designs, GS_M gave a +10% increase in the gain compared with CS when no
297 sire information was available for dams, and a +15% to +27% increase when a
298 proportion of the dams (100% to 25%) had a sire information. When they have known
299 daughters, the estimated breeding values of sires included in the reference population
300 would be more accurate, thus explaining why genomic selection is more favorable.

301 For NM+AI designs, the benefit depended on the sire information completeness. When
302 at least 25% of dams born from natural mating had sire information, GS_M was always
303 beneficial regardless of the AI level: from +10% (AI = 20%) to +19% (AI = 60%). When
304 none of the dams born from natural mating had sire information, GS_M gave a lower
305 gain than CS (-6%). This means that a reference population that includes natural
306 mating sires with no progeny records (inaccurate information) and AI sires (more
307 accurate information) decreases the accuracy of genomic prediction.

308 For NM+AI+PT designs, the benefit depended on both the proportion of known sires
309 and the level of AI. When only 25% of dams born from natural mating had sire
310 information, GS_M gave a lower gain than CS (-4%). When complete sire information
311 was available for the dams, the benefit of GS_M was positive but low, +9%, for the
312 lower AI level (30%), null for the intermediary AI level (60%) and negative, -4%, for the
313 higher AI level (80%). This means that for lower AI rates, the number of inseminated
314 ewes was too low to benefit from the increase in accuracy provided by progeny testing.

315 In Raoul *et al.* (2017), in which only the NM+AI+PT design was modeled with complete
316 pedigree information and 50% of ewes were inseminated, GS_M gave +26% increase
317 in gain compared with CS. Contrary to Raoul *et al.* (2017), the number of AI sires used
318 per year in this study was constant across strategies to take into account constraints
319 due to AI seasonality and the use of fresh semen.

320 For NM+AI and NM+AI+PT designs, when all females had sire information, the genetic
321 gain nearly reached a plateau, $0.188 - 0.191 \sigma_a/y$, regardless of the AI level.

322

323

324 *Benefit of genomic selection strategy based on a male and female reference*
325 *population.*

326 Regardless the design, the proportion of dams born from natural mating with a sire
327 information and the AI level, GS_MF was always favorable. In general the genetic
328 gains expected with 25% of genotyped females were close to those expected with
329 100% of genotyped females. Compared to CS, the increase in gain when implementing
330 a GS_MF scenario was high to very high for NM (36% to 89%) and NM+AI (36 to 60%).

331 For NM+AI+PT, the increase in gain was also high, 30-36% for AI=30% and less
332 important as the AI level was high, +26-28% for AI=60% and +15-21% for AI=80%.

333 In these simulations, females to be genotyped were randomly chosen. Different
334 sampling strategies, based on targeted genotyping of female categories as high
335 genetic value females or less related to the male population, might be assessed but
336 previous studies (e.g. Plieschke *et al.*, 2016) show that random sampling gives higher
337 genetic gains.

338

339 *Comparison across designs*

340 Quinton *et al.* (1992) stated that selection strategies should be compared at similar
341 levels of inbreeding. The optimum, if defined as the maximum genetic gain of a design
342 for a given inbreeding level, could be determined among a range of values for the main
343 parameters. Nevertheless, applying such an approach to stochastic simulations would
344 be very time-consuming.

345 For NM designs, the different strategies (CS, GS_M and GS_MF) were assessed with
346 the same demographic parameters and decision variable selection. The inbreeding
347 levels were low (0.0001 point per year) and similar for all strategies.

348 For NM+AI designs, the number of AI males used per year has a strong effect on both
349 the genetic gain and inbreeding (Raoul and Elsen, 2019). In the present study, the
350 number of AI males used per year was constant for a given level of AI and across
351 strategies. The values were chosen to reflect real French meat sheep breeding
352 programs. Inbreeding levels, comprised between 0.0002 points per year and 0.0004
353 points per year were generally slightly higher for CS than for GS_M and GS_MF but
354 similar for all strategies for a given AI level. As Inbreeding levels were different
355 according the level of AI, caution should be exercised when making comparisons.
356 However, even if input parameters are not identical, the comparison of CS strategies
357 shows that for NM+AI designs, shifting to GS is somewhat more favorable than shifting
358 to NM+AI+PT.

359 For NM+AI+PT designs, shifting from a conventional selection strategy to GS_M or
360 GS_MF implies substantial changes in terms of the management of male animals. AI
361 males are used younger in GS than in CS and the variability of the number of doses
362 per AI male is expected to be higher in CS (some AI males are culled after PT and
363 some are much used as elite reproducers) than in GS. Even if the optimal number of
364 AI sires, for a given AI level, is expected to be lower in GS than in CS, we opted to
365 compare strategies with the same number of AI sires used per year. As in Raoul *et al.*
366 (2017), GS_M and GS_MF led to lesser increase in the inbreeding rate than CS. We
367 assume that comparing strategies at the same level of inbreeding would have favored
368 genomic strategies.

369

370 *Benefit of genomic selection for meat traits*

371 In the present study, we only considered the selection of a maternal trait. In France
372 both meat and maternal traits are selected in meat sheep populations. Each trait is
373 selected separately and no multi-trait index is used. In the present study, we assumed
374 that the selection intensities on meat traits were equal to the currently observed
375 intensities and remained constant across strategies. Selection on meat traits was taken
376 into account as random losses among candidates. We therefore expect that the
377 response to selection on a maternal trait will not be affected by meat trait selection as
378 long as there is no negative genetic correlation between maternal and meat traits. In
379 the GS strategies we modelled, meat phenotypes and genotypes would be available
380 for one-year-old male candidates. This could result in a more accurate estimation of
381 breeding values for meat traits. The optimal use of this genomic information for meat
382 traits needs to be considered in further studies.

383

384 *Practical implementation of GS strategies, economic considerations*

385 In this paper, we show that switching from a CS to a GS strategy (at least to GS_MF
386 strategies) would be profitable for all French meat sheep populations. However,
387 genotyping costs have to be considered. For NM and NM+AI designs, moving to a GS
388 strategy would not modify sire management practices, so the cost-effectiveness of GS
389 depends on the balance between additional genotyping costs and additional genetic
390 gain. For each breed, the economic benefit of GS depends on how the added economic
391 value linked to the additional genetic gain both within and outside of the nucleus offsets
392 the additional costs of breeders. For NM+AI+PT, switching to a GS strategy would
393 change how AI sires are managed and would lower the related costs. NM+AI+PT
394 designs are then more likely to be able to compensate the additional genotyping costs.

395 Approximately two times more candidates were genotyped than the number of males
396 selected for natural mating and AI. To implement the GS_MF strategy, at least 25% of
397 dams have to be genotyped. To reduce costs, candidates (and dams) can be
398 genotyped using cheaper low density SNP chips and their 50K genotypes imputed.
399 Many studies have addressed this possibility in dairy cattle (e.g. Zhang and Druet,
400 2010), sheep (e.g. Hayes *et al.*, 2012) and other species (e.g. Cleveland and Hickey,
401 2013). Our simulation (data not shown) indicated that the imputation step has no effect
402 on the genetic gain evaluated in this study as long as sires and candidates (dams) had
403 respectively 50K and at least 3K SNP genotypes. In some breeds, genomic tests such
404 as parentage certification and parentage assignment (Tortereau *et al.*, 2017), scrapie
405 resistance genetic (Palhière *et al.*, 2004) or hyper-ovulation polymorphism (Martin *et*
406 *al.*, 2014) are already performed. Additional genotyping costs will be breed-dependent
407 and will decrease if the design of low density SNP chip already includes some of the
408 SNPs required for genomic tests.

409

410

411 **Conclusion**

412 In this study, using a stochastic model, we assessed the benefit of genomic selection
413 for a variety of breeding programs that encompass all current French meat sheep
414 populations. For the current designs with no AI or no progeny testing of AI sires, the
415 benefit of genomic selection based on a male reference population was limited when
416 sire information is missing for dams. For current designs that include progeny testing
417 of AI sires, genomic selection based on a male reference population, and hence a
418 discontinuation of progeny testing, was detrimental compared with conventional
419 selection designs when the AI level was high and favorable when the AI level was low.

420 Regardless of the design, genomic selection based on a male and female reference
421 population was favorable and genotyping 25% of the females in the nucleus resulted
422 in a significant increase in gain compared with conventional designs.

423

424

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429

430 **Declaration of interest**

431 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

432

433 **Ethics statement**

434 None

435

436 **Software and data repository resources**

437 None.

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498

499 **Tables**

500

501 **Table 1: Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rates according to the genomic strategy**
 502 **for meat sheep. Natural mating based breeding programs (NM), incomplete and**
 503 **complete pedigree.**

504

Strategy ¹	% of genotyped ♀	% of NM ² ♀ with sire information	Annual genetic gain ($\sigma g/y$)			Inbreeding rate ($\Delta F/y$)
			mean (n=30)	std (n=30)	Ref=100	
CS	0	0	0.081	0.006	100	
CS	0	25	0.083	0.006	102	
CS	0	50	0.086	0.007	106	
CS	0	75	0.099	0.008	121	
CS	0	100	0.116	0.010	142	0.001
PAR_AS	25	25	0.092	0.010	113	
PAR_AS	50	50	0.099	0.009	122	
PAR_AS	75	75	0.107	0.006	131	
PAR_AS	100	100	0.115	0.007	141	0.001
GS_M	0	0	0.089	0.006	110	
GS_M	0	25	0.106	0.008	130	
GS_M	0	50	0.115	0.007	142	
GS_M	0	75	0.121	0.009	149	
GS_M	0	100	0.133	0.009	163	0.001
GS_MF	25	25	0.157	0.010	193	
GS_MF	50	50	0.158	0.008	194	
GS_MF	75	75	0.153	0.009	187	
GS_MF	100	100	0.161	0.008	198	0.001

505 1 CS = conventional strategy; PAR_AS = parentage assignment, the sires of a proportion of
 506 females born from multi-sire matings are assigned. GS_M: genomic selection based on a male
 507 reference population (all sires); GS_MF: genomic selection based on a male and female
 508 reference population (all sires and a proportion of dams)

509 2 NM ♀ = dams born from natural mating.

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512 **Table 2: Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rates according to the genomic strategy**
513 **for meat sheep. Natural mating and AI based breeding programs (NM+AI), dams with**
514 **incomplete sire information.**

Strategy ¹	% AI	Nb of AI ♂ selected per year	% of genotyped ♀	% of NM ♀ ² with sire information	Annual genetic gain ($\sigma g/y$)				Inbreeding rate ($\Delta F/y$) mean (n=30)
					mean (n=30)	std (n=30)	Ref	Ref2	
CS	10	8	0	0	0.118	0.012	100		
CS	10	8	0	25	0.115	0.011	98		
PAR_AS	10	8	25	25	0.124	0.012	105		
PAR_AS	10	8	50	50	0.130	0.012	110		
PAR_AS	10	8	100	100	0.142	0.014	121		0.002
GS_M	10	8	0	0	0.111	0.014	94		
GS_M	10	8	0	25	0.131	0.009	111		
GS_MF	10	8	25	25	0.183	0.012	156		
GS_MF	10	8	50	50	0.180	0.011	153		
GS_MF	10	8	100	100	0.181	0.010	154		0.001
CS	20	8	0	0	0.138	0.017	117	100	
CS	20	8	0	25	0.144	0.017	123	105	
PAR_AS	20	8	25	25	0.144	0.017	123	105	
PAR_AS	20	8	50	50	0.144	0.013	122	104	
PAR_AS	20	8	100	100	0.152	0.016	129	110	0.003
GS_M	20	8	0	0	0.129	0.014	110	93	
GS_M	20	8	0	25	0.159	0.018	135	115	
GS_MF	20	8	25	25	0.217	0.019	185	157	
GS_MF	20	8	50	50	0.215	0.017	183	156	
GS_MF	20	8	100	100	0.213	0.021	181	155	0.002

515 1 CS = conventional strategy; PAR_AS = parentage assignment, the sires of a proportion of
516 females born from multi-sire matings are assigned. GS_M: genomic selection based on a male
517 reference population (all sires); GS_MF: genomic selection based on a male and female
518 reference population (all sires and a proportion of dams)

519 2 NM ♀ = dams born from natural mating.

521 **Table 3: Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rates according to the genomic strategy**
 522 **for meat sheep. Natural mating and AI based breeding programs (NM+AI), dams with**
 523 **complete sire information.**

524

Strategy ¹	% AI	Nb of AI ♂ selected per year	% of genotyped ♀	% of NM ♀ ² with sire information	Annual genetic gain ($\sigma g/y$)				Inbreeding rate ($\Delta F/y$) mean (n=30)
					mean (n=30)	std (n=30)	Ref1	Ref2	
CS	30	8	0	100	0.165	0.022	100		0.004
GS_M	30	8	0	100	0.191	0.020	116		0.003
GS_MF	30	8	25	100	0.230	0.021	140		0.003
GS_MF	30	8	50	100	0.233	0.019	141		0.003
GS_MF	30	8	100	100	0.243	0.018	147		0.003
CS	60	16	0	100	0.158	0.020	96	100	0.002
GS_M	60	16	0	100	0.188	0.016	114	119	0.002
GS_MF	60	16	25	100	0.230	0.014	139	145	0.002
GS_MF	60	16	50	100	0.231	0.015	140	146	0.002
GS_MF	60	16	100	100	0.238	0.015	144	150	0.002

525 1 CS = conventional strategy; GS_M: genomic selection based on a male reference population

526 (all sires); GS_MF: genomic selection based on a male and female reference population (all

527 sires and a proportion of dams)

528 2 NM ♀ = dams born from natural mating.

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531 **Table 4: Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rates according to the genomic strategy**
532 **for meat sheep. Natural mating, AI and progeny testing based breeding programs**
533 **(NM+AI+PT), dams with incomplete sire information.**

534

Strategy ¹	% AI	Nb of AI ♂ selected per year	% of genotyped ♀	% of NM ♀ ² with sire information	Annual genetic gain ($\sigma g/y$)			Inbreeding rate ($\Delta F/y$) mean (n=30)
					mean (n=30)	std (n=30)	Ref1	
CS	30	10;10	0	25	0.170	0.018	100	
CS	30	10;10	0	100	0.175	0.016	103	
PAR_AS	30	10;10	25	25	0.167	0.018	98	
PAR_AS	30	10;10	50	50	0.171	0.018	100	
PAR_AS	30	10;10	100	100	0.176	0.015	103	0.005
GS_M	30	10	0	25	0.164	0.022	97	
GS_M	30	10	0	100	0.191	0.016	112	
GS_MF	30	10	25	25	0.224	0.018	132	
GS_MF	30	10	50	50	0.232	0.019	136	
GS_MF	30	10	100	100	0.238	0.018	140	0.003

535 1 CS = conventional strategy; PAR_AS = parentage assignment, the sires of a proportion of
536 females born from multi-sire matings are assigned. GS_M: genomic selection based on a male
537 reference population (all sires); GS_MF: genomic selection based on a male and female
538 reference population (all sires and a proportion of dams)

539 2 NM ♀ = dams born from natural mating.

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Table 5: Annual genetic gain and inbreeding rates according to the genomic strategy for meat sheep. Natural mating, AI and progeny testing based breeding programs (NM+AI+PT), dams with complete sire information.

Strategy ¹	% AI	Nb of AI ♂ selected per year	% of genotyped ♀	% of NM ♀ ² with sire information	Annual genetic gain ($\sigma g/y$)			Inbreeding rate ($\Delta F/y$) mean (n=30)
					mean (n=30)	std (n=30)	Ref	
CS	30	10;10	0	100	0.175	0.016	100	0.005
GS_M	30	10	0	100	0.191	0.016	109	0.003
GS_MF	30	10	25	100	0.227	0.014	130	0.003
GS_MF	30	10	50	100	0.235	0.022	134	0.003
GS_MF	30	10	100	100	0.238	0.018	136	0.003
CS	60	20;10	0	100	0.189	0.017	108	0.006
GS_M	60	15	0	100	0.190	0.015	108	0.003
GS_MF	60	15	25	100	0.238	0.017	136	0.003
GS_MF	60	15	50	100	0.240	0.014	137	0.003
GS_MF	60	15	100	100	0.241	0.013	138	0.003
CS	80	26;10	0	100	0.197	0.020	112	0.005
GS_M	80	18	0	100	0.189	0.017	108	0.003
GS_MF	80	18	25	100	0.226	0.014	129	0.003
GS_MF	80	18	50	100	0.233	0.014	133	0.002
GS_MF	80	18	100	100	0.238	0.011	136	0.002

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1 CS = conventional strategy; GS_M: genomic selection based on a male reference population (all sires); GS_MF: genomic selection based on a male and female reference population (all sires and a proportion of dams)

2 NM ♀ = dams born from natural mating.

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560 **The levels of artificial insemination and missing sire information makes**

561 **Genomic selection not always beneficial in meat sheep**

562 J. Raoul and J.M. Elsen

563

564 **Supplementary material S1: typology of meat sheep breeding programs in**

565 **France**

566 All meat sheep breeds in France include maternal traits, such as prolificacy and pre-
567 weaning weight, in their breeding goals (Cheype et al., 2013). Even for highly
568 specialized meat breeds that are bred both for terminal and maternal uses, maternal
569 traits are the priority traits. Breeding programs are diverse in terms of population size,
570 pedigree data, sire selection processes and the use of artificial insemination (AI): the
571 rate of inseminated ewes is very variable between breeds with a continuum from
572 breeding programs based exclusively on natural mating to programs that include AI
573 with AI rates ranging from a few percent to 80%. Pedigrees are generally well recorded
574 in specialized meat breeds but, for hardy breeds, part of the sire information for ewes
575 is often missing. The rate of missing sire information can be very high and reach up to
576 90%. Independently from size and pedigree completeness considerations, not all meat
577 breed populations implement selection based on progeny testing even if AI is used.
578 Only 3 breeds currently implement progeny testing of their AI males for the maternal
579 traits, and the number of progeny-tested males per year ranges from 10 to 30.

580 French meat sheep breeding programs are all based on the collective management of
581 male pathway. The best young male candidates are first selected based on their
582 parents' mean EBVs for maternal traits among lambs born from assortative mating.

583 Young candidates are bred for several months in a purebred central test station where
584 sorting is applied based on the functional traits and breed standards (characteristics
585 which may be considered as independent from the main selection objective). If meat
586 traits are included in the breeding goal, meat phenotypes are recorded at the central
587 test station and young males are selected based on their own records. For AI based
588 breeding programs, males for AI are selected prior to males for natural mating (NM).
589 Fresh semen is used exclusively. For a few breeds, an additional step of selection is
590 performed for AI sires, based on progeny testing (PT) for meat and/or maternal traits.
591 Supplementary Table 1 reports the official characteristics of the main French sheep
592 breeding programs (Loywyck *et al.*, 2019): breeding program design, proportion of
593 lambs born from inseminated ewes, proportion of lambs with sire information and size
594 of the nucleus.

595

596 **Supplementary material S2: details of modelling method**

597 To compare different designs of breeding programs, we developed a stochastic
598 simulation model where individuals, including their genome, were simulated. The
599 method used in Raoul *et al.* (2017) was adapted to designs assessed in this study.
600 Stochastic events were simulated using the NAG FORTRAN library (the Numerical
601 Algorithms Group (NAG), Oxford, UK). Parents were randomly mated and
602 replacements randomly selected during 10 reproductive cycles to establish a founder
603 population with a given demographic structure. Ten years of selection for a maternal
604 trait were then simulated by applying a conventional design (CS). The next 15 years
605 were simulated by applying either a conventional or a genomic strategy.

606

607 *Founder population*

608 A total of 11,816 real genotypes of 54,241 bi-allelic SNPs (Illumina OvineSNP50
609 BeadChip -Illumina ©) from progeny-tested sires of the dairy Lacaune sheep breed
610 were used to initialize population genomes (initial population). The genotypes were
611 cleaned (call frequency ≥ 0.95 , Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, Mendelian inheritance
612 compatibilities) and only autosomal SNPs having a known position on the genome
613 were retained: 47,706 SNPs were used for the genome simulations. Using
614 genealogical information, phased chromosomes were obtained from Fimpute
615 (Sargolzaei et al., 2014). At Time -10, the phased genome of 5,000 individuals were
616 randomly selected among the 11,816 individuals and a randomly assigned sex were
617 used as a starting point for each simulation run.

618 To obtain the desired demographic structure, 10 random mating cycles from Time -10
619 to Time 0 were performed. At each cycle, 1500 females were randomly selected as
620 dams and randomly mated to 100 sires that were selected among males born in the
621 previous years. The parental gametes were generated to produce new individual
622 genomes: the number of crossovers was simulated following a Poisson distribution
623 $P(\lambda)$ with λ the chromosome length expressed in Morgan. Positions of the crossovers
624 were allocated following a uniform distribution along the chromosome and a parental
625 strand was randomly chosen (*i.e.* paternal or maternal) to start the haplotype
626 reconstruction of the gamete. Mutations were not simulated. At Time 0, founders were
627 randomly selected according to a demographic structure (*i.e.* percentage of individuals
628 per age-category) among individuals that were created in the last seven cycles, aged
629 from 1 to 7 years old at Time 0.

630

631 *Quantitative trait loci and phenotype simulation*

632 One thousand quantitative trait loci (QTL) underlying the maternal trait under selection

633 were randomly selected among SNPs with a minor allele frequency higher or equal to
634 0.05. Following Hayes and Goddard (2001), QTL effects were drawn from a Gamma
635 distribution with a shape parameter of 0.4 and a scale parameter of 1.66. Assuming (i)
636 no dominance effect, (ii) Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and (iii) all the additive variance
637 is explained by the QTL, the additive genetic variance was $VA = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{qtl}} 2p_i(1 - p_i)q_i^2$
638 (Falconer, 1960) where p_i denotes the allele frequency of the first allele for QTL i and
639 q_i its effect. The QTL effects were rescaled to make the additive variance VA equal to
640 1. The maternal permanent effects, pe , were drawn from a normal distribution with
641 mean 0 and variance $\frac{rep-h^2}{h^2}$ where $rep = 0.2$ and $h^2 = 0.1$ denote the repeatability and
642 the heritability of the trait. The year by flock effects yfe were drawn from a normal
643 distribution with mean 0 and variance 1. The residual effects e were drawn from a
644 normal distribution with mean 0 and variance $\frac{1-rep}{h^2} - 1$. The k^{th} phenotype y_{jyfk} of a
645 female j , mated in the flock f at year y , was simulated as $y_{jyfk} = TBV_j + pe_j + yfe_{yf} +$
646 e_{jyfk} with TBV_j the true breeding value depending on the effects of all QTL and the
647 female genotype. Only fertile females had a phenotype.

648

649 *Estimation of breeding values*

650 The estimation of breeding values was based on an animal best linear unbiased
651 prediction (BLUP) model (Henderson, 1975) for the conventional (CS) and the
652 parentage assignment (PAR_AS) strategies. The estimation of genomic breeding
653 values was based on an animal single step genomic best linear unbiased prediction
654 (ssGBLUP) model (Aguilar et al., 2010) for the genomic (GS_M and GS_MF)
655 strategies. Both types of evaluation were performed using the Blupf90 software
656 developed by Misztal et al (1999). The genomic relationship matrix was built following

657 Van Raden (2008). Coefficients of inbreeding based on pedigree information were
658 computed using the methodology developed by Aguilar and Misztal (2008) and
659 implemented in the Blupf90 software.

660

661 *Female population structure*

662 Females that were naturally mated had a fertility rate of 90%. In AI based breeding
663 programs, females sorted to be inseminated had a fertility rate of 55%. To mimic the
664 variation in the AI dose production per male, the inseminated dams were randomly
665 allocated to one AI sire with a maximum number of AI per male equal to 140 for 2-year
666 old sires and to 500 for older sires. Females that did not conceive to AI and females
667 not selected for AI were then randomly mated to natural mating sires allocated to their
668 flock assuming a fertility rate of 90%. The average number of females per naturally-
669 mated sire was equal to 35. To prevent inbreeding, a male (AI or natural mating) could
670 not be mated to a female belonging to its dam's flock. The number of progeny per dam
671 depended on the reproduction mode (induced or natural estrus) and parity (first versus
672 second and more). At each cycle, some dams were randomly culled with a proportion
673 varying from 0.10 after parity 1 to 0.50 on average after parity 6. The maximum parity
674 was 7 and around 24% of dams were replaced per cycle. Replacement females were
675 allocated to their dam's flock. There is no difference between the classical and genomic
676 designs regarding how females were selected.

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710 **Supplementary table S1: characteristics of the main French sheep breeding programs.**

711

Breed	Current design for maternal traits ¹	% of lambing from AI sires	% of lambing with known sire	Nucleus size
Blanc du Massif Central	NM+AI+PT	15.4	31.8	20,322
Ile de France	NM+AI+PT	18.1	85.5	9,762
Lacaune ²	NM+AI+PT	43.0	48.6	19,276
Berrichon du Cher Français	NM+AI	33.2	87.5	2,949
Mouton Charollais	NM+AI	14.2	96.8	6,781
Rouge de l'Ouest	NM+AI	16.2	74.5	3,576
Suffolk	NM+AI	16.4	94.0	3,072
Mouton Vendéen	NM+AI	13.5	88.4	6,896
Texel	NM+AI	11.4	97.5	4,052
Romane	NM+AI	9.0	22.0	26,017
Limousine	NM+AI	6.3	39.3	7,401
Caussearde du Lot	NM+AI	6.2	6.3	26,538
Est à Laine Merinos	NM+AI	6.7	23.3	2,985
Grivette	NM		37.3	5,728
Rava	NM		39.2	8,220
Noire du Velay	NM		33.5	5,706
Tarasconnaise	NM		21.5	7,025
PréAlpes du sud	NM		16.2	4,456
Mer. Arles	NM		6.2	11,997

712 ¹ NM = Natural mating, NM+AI = NM+Artificial Insemination, NM+AI+PT = NM+AI+Progeny

713 testing of AI sires

714 ² The lacaune meat sheep population under selection is divided into two nuclei. The proportion
715 of lambing from AI sires is an average resulting from two different proportions of inseminated
716 ewes (60% and 80%)

